

Study on Parenting Styles and Academic Motivation in Secondary and Higher Secondary School Students

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ABSTRACT:

Academic motivation is an important topic that has been debated in hopes of raising levels among students, particularly in their high school time. It can be influenced by a variety of circumstances, including the student's perception of their parent's parenting style. And parenting style plays a crucial role in the child's development and educational background, especially during this pandemic as most students, spent their time with their parents, in-home environment rather than in the school environment. This study aims to investigate the determinants of academic motivation with an emphasis on the role of four parenting styles i.e., authoritative, authoritarian, permissive, and negligent parenting styles among students. The sample size is 330 (male=176, female=154) and they were collected from secondary school and higher secondary school students i.e. (9th std – 12th std). The tools used for the study were Academic Motivation Scale (AMS-HS 28) by Robert J Vallerand, 1993, and Parenting Style Questionnaire by Abdul Gafoor K & Abidha Kurukkan, 2004 which was administered to students. The findings of the present study indicated that there exists no significant relationship between parenting styles and academic motivation in secondary and higher secondary school students. The need for the study is to bring forward the importance of parenting styles among parents, guardians and also among teachers and institutions and to bring awareness of how their involvement, rules and attitudes toward their children contribute to their academics.

Keywords: *Authoritarian, Authoritative, Permissive, Negligent, Academic motivation*

Ever since the concept of parenting was raised, it has been universally playing a crucial role in not only children's life but also in the parent's life. With the increasing knowledge and research on parenting, it is being considered as skills that every parent must hone through training and practices. This made parents to struggle to become the 'perfect' mother or father. But perfection isn't even the goal for parents and children. Without a characterized thumb-rule to consummate parenting, this is a challenge.

Many aspects of a child's life can be influenced by the way a parent raises their child. Academic motivation is one area where parenting style can have a significant impact. This is significant because one's upbringing influences their attitude, outlook, future goals, and performance in the classroom. This could have long-term consequences for the child in social, emotional, mental, physical, educational, and other areas. The uncommon effect on parents and their children was found in this COVID-19. In overnight parents became involved in their children's education, as schools were temporarily closed and moved classes to online mode.

Many numbers of studies have done on finding the relationship between parenting style and academic motivation (Jinbao Tang, 2018; Amare M Mihret, 2019; Margaret M Buoy, 2013, Stephanie Rubin, 2017). And these studies led to the conclusions that parenting style have major effect on children's academic motivation. According to Victor-Aigbodion Vera, Ngwoke Dominic Ugwoke, Nnamani Ogechi, and Adaogu Justina's research, there is a significant correlation between an authoritative parenting style and academic motivation in secondary school teenagers in the state of Edo. Second, authoritarian parenting style has positive relation with academic motivation. Third, permissive parenting style has non-significant positive relation with academic motivation. And the last parenting style, uninvolved had negative correlation with academic motivation.

This study aims to find the relation between parenting style and academic motivation among secondary and higher secondary school students.

Parenting Styles:

Parenting style is most important yet most under developed concept in Indian context. Most of the parents, teachers and students are not at all aware of the concept of parenting styles and how the dimensions work and how it influences the student's personality, academic motivation, temperament, achievement, etc. It has received a good amount of research work already. Many researchers proved that parenting styles have a major impact on children's life right from the birth to their developmental stages. Parenting style is defined as a constellation of parents' attitudes and behaviors toward children and an emotional climate in which the parents' behaviors are expressed (Darling and Steinberg, 1993).

The most predominant theory of parenting styles that we follow even today is Baumrind's parenting styles. After several studies and interviewing parents using Likert scales, factor analyses of the data from European American samples identified the two major dimensions of parenting. Since the reliability

of the findings were impressive, the two influential literature reviews one in late 1970s and another in early 1980s, concluded the two dimensions which was labeled as parental support or parental responsiveness and parental control or parental demandingness.

The first dimension: Demandingness, refers to how parents expect their children to behave matured through their parental supervision and disciplining them and also controlling their behavioral issues of their children. The second dimension: Responsiveness, represents the amount or degree of autonomy they give to their children to be independent through acknowledging and responding to their children's needs, interests and demands.

Using these two dimensions, Baumrind (2011), Maccoby & Martin (2018) have recognized a typology of parenting styles and classified it into the four types i.e., Authoritarian, Authoritative, Permissive and Negligent parenting styles. All the four parenting styles rely upon the balance of responsiveness and demandingness.

Authoritative parenting is characterized by high demandingness and high responsiveness. They tend to be warm and receptive; that will lead to higher educational achievement. Characteristics of authoritative parenting include: lively and happy disposition, self-confident about ability to master tasks, well developed emotion regulation and developed social skills. (Maccoby & Martin, 2018). authoritarian parenting style is characterized by high demandingness and low responsiveness. They tend to shape, control and evaluate the behavior and attitudes of the child by a set standard of conduct, usually an absolute standard, theologically motivated and formulated by a higher authority (Baumrind, 2011). Permissive parenting style is characterized by low demandingness and high responsiveness. Baumrind (2011) explains that permissive parents "behave in a non-punitive, acceptant, affirmative manner towards the child's impulses, desires, and actions". Neglectful parenting style is considered to be low demandingness and low responsiveness. They do not support or encourage their child's self-regulation, and also often fail to monitor or supervise the child's behavior (Maccoby and Martin, 1983).

Among the four parenting styles, many researches have proved that authoritative parenting styles yields the most positive child outcomes and also it plays a predominant role in academic motivation among students.

Researchers have found that most of the European American parents adopt authoritative parenting style and Asian American parents adopt authoritarian parenting style.

Academic Motivation:

Motivation is a very essential component and a key element to operate any organism's behaviors. It causes you to act, whether it's getting a glass of water to minimize thirst or perusing a book to amass information. It includes the natural, near home, social, and mental powers that enact conduct. According to Woodworth, "Motivation is the state of the individual which disposes him to certain behavior for seeking a goal." As Woodworth says, motivation plays an important role in an individual's goal-seeking behavior, it also plays a predominant role in an individual's academic and learning new information which is challenging and brings pleasure to them. Academic motivation is defined by a student's desire (as reflected in the approach, persistence, and level of interest) regarding academic subjects when the student's competence is judged against a standard of performance or excellence (McClelland, et al., 1953). A study by Alexandra L. Nickolauson, 2021 stated that "The lack of motivation in high schoolers has increased in the last ten years."

A prominent theory on academic motivation is given by Edward L. Deci and Richard Ryan, in the mid-1980s called Self-Determination theory (SDT). SDT is a general theory of human motivation and personality that emphasizes people's innate psychological needs and impulses to evolve. It is concerned with the motivations that drive people's decisions in the absence of external pressures and distractions. SDT focuses on how self-motivated and self-determined human behavior is. (Ryan, Deci, 2000)

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. Jinbao Tang (2018) conducted a study on Parenting styles and academic motivation among high school students and their parents. Participants were 226 10th grade students and one respective parent from 3 Chinese urban public school. They have used Academic Motivation Scale and also measured parenting styles scale by Reitman et al. According to the findings, authoritative parenting was positively connected to intrinsic motivation, whereas authoritarian parenting was negatively related to internal and external regulation. Permissive parenting by both mothers and fathers was found to be positively related to external regulation.
2. Victor-Aigbodion Vera conducted research in Edo State, Nigeria, on the relationship between parenting styles and academic motivation among in-school adolescents. Sample consists of 936 SS2 in-school adolescents of both genders. The Parenting style self-report inventory scale (PSSIS) and the Academic motivation self-report inventory (AMSI) were used to collect data from students. The findings revealed that authoritarian parenting is the most common parenting style in families, that authoritative parenting style has a significant relationship with female academic motivation, and that uninvolved parenting style has a strong and negative relationship with student academic motivation.
3. Amare Misganaw Mihret (2019) investigated the relationship between adolescent motivation for academic achievement and parental styles. Data was collected from 192 adolescents who were chosen at random. The achievement motivation self-report instrument and the parenting style scale were utilised as questionnaires. The findings revealed that authoritarian and authoritative parenting styles have a significant relationship with adolescents' academic motivation, while neglectful parenting has a negative impact on students' academic motivation. Indulgent parenting style has no significant relationship with students' academic motivation.

4. Margaret M. Buoy (2013) researched the impact of parental participation on college students' academic motivation and accomplishment. The questionnaires of Perceptions of Parental Autonomy-Support and Control Scale and the Academic Motivation Scale were given to 115 UG students and asked them to fill those. Results showed that students with low parental support had lower scores on motivation and that students who had high parental control had scores significantly higher on amotivation.
5. Stephanie Rubin (2017) has led a study on the connection between academic motivation and parenting styles in various socioeconomic status areas. These outcomes exhibited that the subject's parents who adopted authoritative parenting had higher academic motivation than compared to the one who had authoritarian or permissive parents. The questionnaires were given to UG students at Rowan University namely, Motivated Strategies for Learning Questionnaire Subscales and Parenting Style Questionnaire.
6. Tawsif Khan (2020) researched the role of parenting styles in student's academic motivation. His research was carried out in the Malakand district. 160 samples were chosen and collected their demographic information form, a parenting style questionnaire, and an academic motivation scale. The research reported that authoritative parenting style plays a predominant role in academic motivation among students and it also increases academic motivation, whereas authoritarian parenting style decreases student's academic motivation.
7. Ranjeet Kumar (2017) conducted a study on Academic Motivation and Parenting Styles and socio-economic status on secondary students (30% - female, 70% - male) of government students Muzaffarpur district Head Quarter. The tests revealed that students who have authoritative parenting will have higher academic motivation level in UG when compared to the students who have authoritarian or permissive parenting. These results also suggest that socioeconomic status does not affect the motivation level of the UG students.
8. Thienhuong N. Hoang (2007) has conducted research on relationship between parenting styles and motivation in adolescents. The participants were from Norther California High School students who took Algebra I course. 140 students were given Perceived Parenting Style Scale and motivation scale to fill out. The result stated that authoritative parenting has positive relation with student's motivational patterns.
9. A study by Mehezabin Dordi (2018) on finding the relationship of parenting styles with personality and academic motivation among adolescents showed that students have positive correlation between authoritative parenting and intrinsic motivation. The sample was collected from 60 adolescents aged 13 to 19 years from Mumbai city by giving the questionnaires of Parental Authority, Big Five and The Academic Motivation, which were administered to students.
10. Jewrell Rivers (2012) investigated the association between parental styles and teenage academic performance. The sample consists of 148 high school students from rural, south-central state, ranging from ages 14 to 18. The questionnaires used were the parenting style and Parental Involvement questionnaire (PSPI), Patterns of Adapted Learning Survey (PALS) and Harter's Intrinsic-Extrinsic Orientation Scale administered to students. Adolescents who reported their parents having a more authoritative parenting style demonstrated greater intrinsic motivation in their academic pursuits.

METHODOLOGY

Need for the study:

Every child's behavior, attitudes, thoughts, motivations arise from their home environment. Parents play a crucial and inevitable role in children right from their birth to their further developmental stages. The parenting styles that a child's parent adopt has an influential effect on their academic motivation. So, this study aims at exploring how secondary and higher secondary students perceive their mother's and father's parenting style and how their parenting style impact their academic motivation. It helps students how to cope up with their parental pressure and be able to perform their school tasks even if there are no expectations or provision of support and attention from their parents. It also helps parents to become more aware about how their involvement towards their children contribute to their children's academic motivation.

Objective:

1. To identify the most prevalent parenting style that is been adopted in the sample size
2. To identify whether there exists a positive or negative or no relation between the four parenting styles i.e., authoritative, authoritarian, negligent and indulgent and motivation and amotivation.

Hypothesis:

- H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and academic motivation
- H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between authoritarian parenting style and academic motivation
- H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between negligent parenting style and academic motivation
- H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between permissive parenting style and academic motivation

Research Design:

A correlational research approach was used in this study to examine how parental styles affect academic motivation. This research design is been implemented to proceed with the study because it only investigates the relationship between the variables without manipulating or controlling any variable. This study also shows whether the four different kinds of parenting styles have significant or non-significant positive or negative relation with the extrinsic, intrinsic and amotivation.

Variables:

- Parenting Styles – Authoritative, Authoritarian, Permissive and Negligent
- Academic motivation

Sample:

The sample were collected using purposive sampling technique. Purposive sampling is a non-probability sampling method where the samples are chosen from specific range of age, gender or any specific characteristics of the individuals. The sample group comprised of 330 secondary and higher secondary school students (9th to 12th grade students), of which 154 participants were female (46.7%) and 176 were male participants (53.3%). Participants were from 3 different schools of Coimbatore, Pondicherry and Thrissur districts. Only samples who have been volunteered to participate and got consent from the respective school principal stating that they have informed to their parents have been included in the study. The data was collected in person from each student in classroom setting.

Instruments:

Two measures were used in this study,

1. **Scale of parenting styles:** The Scale of Parenting Styles is to measure the perceived parenting style of the subject's parents (mother and father), which was developed by Abdul Gafoor & Abidha Kurukkan, 2014. It consists of 38 statements, which describes how the subject perceives his/her mother and father is dealing with them. It is a 5-point scale so the subject has to read each statement and answer 'Very right' (5), 'Mostly right' (4), 'Sometimes right, sometimes wrong' (3), 'Mostly wrong' (2), 'Very wrong' (1) that best describes his/her mother and father in dealing with them. This scale is administered to secondary and higher secondary school students. This has construct validity. The responsiveness subscale's validity coefficient is found to be 0.80, whereas the control subscale's is 0.76. The value for responsiveness is said to be 0.81 and for control is 0.83.
2. **Academic Motivation Scale:** The Academic Motivation Scale (AMS-HS 28) was developed by Vallerand et al., 1992. It consists of 28 items which measures the 3 dimensions of motivation, namely extrinsic, intrinsic and amotivation by examining why students go to school. It is 7-point scale and a subject should read each statement and answer "Not at all" (1) to "exactly" (7) with the midpoint at "Moderately" (4). This scale is administered to high school students. The test-retest coefficient of reliability is 0.79. the internal consistency of the subscales was tested using Cronbach alpha. The value is 0.80.

Procedure:

The data was collected from 330 secondary and higher secondary students by the following steps: The purpose of the study and instructions on how to fill the questionnaires were explained to the subjects until they were clear on how to do it. Prior to giving the questionnaires, consent has been taken from the respective school Principal and their parents and students and only the subject's responses are taken into account. Then, the participants were seated comfortably. Demographic details, Scale of Parenting Style and Academic Motivation Scale been given to them and asked to fill out by reading each question carefully. The participants took around 30 mins to complete the questionnaires. After the completion of test, the participants were made assure that the information pertains to the individual's identity will not be revealed and remains confidential.

Data were analyzed by SPSS statistics software. The relation between parenting style and academic motivation is tested with Pearson correlation.

Results

Table 1 shows the distribution of the samples across the Demographics factors

GENDER	N	PERCENTAGE
MALE	176	53.3
FEMALE	154	46.7
N	330	

Table 2 shows the relationship between authoritative parenting style and academic motivation

Correlations

		AUTHORITATIVE	EXTRINSIC	INTRINSIC	AMOTIVATION
AUTHORITATIVE	Pearson Correlation	1	.090	.009	.164
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.338	.926	.079
	N	115	115	115	115
EXTRINSIC	Pearson Correlation	.090	1	.768**	.091
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.338		.000	.336
	N	115	115	115	115
INTRINSIC	Pearson Correlation	.009	.768**	1	.041
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.926	.000		.661
	N	115	115	115	115
AMOTIVATION	Pearson Correlation	.164	.091	.041	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.079	.336	.661	
	N	115	115	115	115

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

GRDAE	N	PERCENTAGE
9	85	25.8
10	81	24.5
11	106	32.1
12	58	17.6

Here, the sample size is 330 and targeted group is between 9th std and 12th std. From the data, 53.3% are male and 46.7% are female. Based on grade factor, 25.8% individuals are studying 9th std, 24.5% are in 10th grade, 32.1% students are in 11th grade and 17.6% students are in 12th grade.

Table 1.1 shows the distribution of the samples across the Parenting Styles

PSQ		N	PERCENTAGE
AUTHORITATIVE	MALE	55	47.8
	FEMALE	60	52.2
	TOTAL	115	100.0
AUTHORITARIAN	MALE	8	47.1
	FEMALE	9	52.9
	TOTAL	17	100.0
NEGLIGENT	MALE	81	58.7
	FEMALE	57	41.3
	TOTAL	138	100.0
INDULGENT	MALE	34	56.7
	FEMALE	26	43.3
	TOTAL	60	100.0

N= 330

Among the total sample of 330, 115 individuals are nurtured under authoritative parenting style, 17 individuals were under authoritarian parenting style, 138 students were under negligent parenting style and 60 were under indulgent parenting style.

From Table 1.1, it is evident that the most prevalent parenting style that is been adopted by the student's parents is Negligent and the least preferred parenting style is the Authoritarian style among secondary and higher secondary school students.

As a thumb rule, coefficient is statistically significant if its "Sig (2 tailed) value is <0.01. From the above table for authoritative parenting style the correlation with its extrinsic motivation is .090 but the p value is .338 which is > 0.01. This correlation is too small to accept the alternative hypothesis. So, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, we conclude that authoritative parenting style has non-significant correlation with extrinsic motivation.

Similarly, for authoritative parenting style its correlation is .009 with intrinsic motivation which indicates that they have positive relation between them, but the p value is .926, which is >0.01. The correlation value is too small to accept the alternative hypothesis. So, the null hypothesis is accepted. Hence, we can say that the authoritative parenting style and intrinsic motivation has non-significant correlation with intrinsic motivation.

The correlation between authoritative parenting style and amotivation is 0.164, which says that they have positive relation between them and its p value is .079, which is > 0.01 . Hence, we can say that authoritative parenting style has non-significant correlation with amotivation.

Hence, from Table 2 we can conclude that authoritative parenting style has non-significant positive correlation with academic motivation.

Table 3 shows the relationship between authoritarian parenting style and academic motivation

Correlations

		AUTHORITARIAN	EXTRINSIC	INTRINSIC	AMOTIVATION
AUTHORITARIAN	Pearson Correlation	1	.103	.146	.146
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.693	.575	.576
	N	17	17	17	17
EXTRINSIC	Pearson Correlation	.103	1	.874**	-.364
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.693		.000	.151
	N	17	17	17	17
INTRINSIC	Pearson Correlation	.146	.874**	1	-.107
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.575	.000		.683
	N	17	17	17	17
AMOTIVATION	Pearson Correlation	.146	-.364	-.107	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.576	.151	.683	
	N	17	17	17	17

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above table is a Pearson correlation between authoritarian, extrinsic, intrinsic, and amotivation. Pearson's coefficient is usually between +1 and -1, where +1 is a perfect positive correlation, and -1 is a perfect negative correlation. 0 means there is no linear correlation at all.

The Pearson coefficient between the authoritarian and extrinsic is 0.103 from which we can decipher that there is a positive correlation between authoritarian and extrinsic motivation. But the p value is 0.693 which is > 0.01 . The that means the correlation between authoritarian and extrinsic motivation is non-significant.

While the coefficient between the authoritarian and intrinsic is 0.146 which interprets that there is a positive correlation between the authoritarian and intrinsic motivation. But the p value is 0.575 which is > 0.01 , that means the correlation is not significant.

The Pearson coefficient is 0.146 between the authoritarian and amotivation depicts that there is a positive correlation between them. The p value for the correlation is .576 which means that the correlation between authoritarian parenting style and amotivation is non-significant.

Hence, we can conclude that authoritarian parenting style has non-significant correlation with academic motivation.

Table 4 shows the relationship between indulgent parenting style and academic motivation**Correlations**

		INDULGENT	EXTRINSIC	INTRINSIC	AMOTIVATION
INDULGENT	Pearson Correlation	1	-.184	-.202	.057
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.160	.122	.665
	N	60	60	60	60
EXTRINSIC	Pearson Correlation	-.184	1	.755**	.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.160		.000	.999
	N	60	138	138	138
INTRINSIC	Pearson Correlation	-.202	.755**	1	.038
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.122	.000		.654
	N	60	138	138	138
AMOTIVATION	Pearson Correlation	.057	.000	.038	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.665	.999	.654	
	N	60	138	138	138

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

As a thumb rule, coefficient is statistically significant if its "Sig (2 tailed) value is <0.01 . From the above table, for indulgent parenting style its correlation with extrinsic motivation is -0.184 from which we can interpret that there is a negative correlation between indulgent parenting style and extrinsic motivation. But the p value is $.160$ which is >0.01 , so we accept the null hypothesis. That means the correlation is non-significant between indulgent parenting style and extrinsic motivation.

The coefficient value for indulgent parenting and intrinsic motivation is -0.202 from which we can decipher that there is negative correlation between indulgent parenting and intrinsic motivation. But the p value is $.122$ which is >0.01 , so we accept the null hypothesis. This means that the correlation between indulgent parenting style and intrinsic motivation is non-significant.

Similarly, the R value of indulgent and amotivation is $.057$ and from which we can say that they have positive correlation between them. The p value is $.665$ which is >0.01 , so we accept the null hypothesis. That means the correlation between indulgent parenting style and amotivation is non-significant.

Hence, we can conclude that indulgent parenting has non-significant relationship with extrinsic, intrinsic motivation and amotivation.

Table 5 shows the relationship between negligent parenting style and academic motivation**Correlations**

		NEGLIGENT	EXTRINSIC	INTRINSIC	AMOTIVATION
NEGLIGENT	Pearson Correlation	1	.101	.128	-.044
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.444	.328	.739
	N	138	60	60	60
EXTRINSIC	Pearson Correlation	.101	1	.755**	-.191
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.444		.000	.144
	N	60	60	60	60
INTRINSIC	Pearson Correlation	.128	.755**	1	-.078
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.328	.000		.555
	N	60	60	60	60
AMOTIVATION	Pearson Correlation	-.044	-.191	-.078	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.739	.144	.555	
	N	60	60	60	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The above table is a Pearson correlation between negligent, extrinsic, intrinsic, and amotivation. Pearson's coefficient is usually between $+1$ and -1 , where $+1$ is a perfect positive correlation, and -1 is a perfect negative correlation. 0 means there is no linear correlation at all.

The Pearson coefficient between the negligent and extrinsic is 0.101 from which we can decipher that there is a positive correlation between negligent and extrinsic. The 2-tailed significance value also called the p-value between the negligent and extrinsic is 0.444 and the standard alpha value is 0.01 and our p-value is higher than the alpha value which means that our correlation is not significant.

While the coefficient between the negligent and intrinsic is 0.128 which interprets that there is a positive correlation between the negligent and intrinsic. While the p-value between the negligent and intrinsic is 0.328 which is higher than the 0.01 which depicts that it's not significant.

The Pearson coefficient of -.044 between the negligent and amotivation depicts that there is a negative correlation between them. The p-value of 0.739 is between the negligent and amotivation and it's higher than our alpha value of 0.01 which decipher that it's not significant

Hence, the negligent parenting style has non-significant relation with extrinsic and intrinsic motivation and amotivation.

Discussion

The concept of parenting style is skewed by culture. So, even within the same culture, drawing generalisations about a group of people is very difficult. Parents are children's foundation. Children learn most of the things from their parents and in-home environment. It nurtures one's personality, attitudes, thoughts, academic motivation, and performance.

The study aims to find the relationship between authoritarian, authoritative, indulgent and negligent parenting styles in the context to the Indian parenting style. The questionnaire used for the present study is Scale of parenting styles developed by Abdul Gafoor and Abidha Kurukkan which is based on Indian circumstances. It is used to measure the perceived parenting style of the subject's parents (mother and father). The other questionnaire used is the Academic motivation scale developed by Vallerand et al., 1992 based on the Western context. A questionnaire based on the Indian setting wasn't available therefore this particular questionnaire has been used. The citations for this certain scale are 4006 and has been used in various studies from diverse culture.

This study revealed that the negligent parenting style is the most common, followed by the authoritative parenting style and indulgent parenting style among the study sample. The least common parenting approach is authoritarian. Contrary to the present findings Janani Rangarajan et al (2020) conducted a study on parents who have been NICU graduates and reported that the authoritative parenting style is the most common parenting style among the sample. Similarly, according to the study conducted by Koyel Mandal (2021), the authoritative parenting style is the most predominately practiced parenting style. Due to so many working parents in the study sample, I suspect that the working conditions of parents made them spend little time or little energy concentrating on their child, and in turn, they adopted a negligent parenting style. And not only the work environment but also other reasons such as financial hardships, interpersonal relationships between spouses, maybe the parent have been raised by neglectful parenting or when a parent deals with mental health issues that may prevent create bonding with their children and also other crisis which may have led them to adopt negligent parenting style.

The present study revealed a non-significant relationship between authoritative parenting style and academic motivation among secondary and higher secondary school students. Contrary to this result, Erlanger Turner (2009) The impact of parenting styles, achievement motivation and self-efficacy was studied on college students' academic performance. The data were collected from 264 students. The result showed that authoritative parenting influences academic motivation and self-efficacy.

Furthermore, the study indicates a non-significant relationship between authoritarian parenting style and academic motivation among secondary and higher secondary school students. Contrary to this result, a study conducted by Tawsif Khan (2020) on the role of parenting styles in student's academic motivation it was evident that authoritarian parenting style decreases student's academic motivation.

In this study, it is found that indulgent parenting style has non-significant negative relation with academic motivation and non-significant positive relation with amotivation. Contrary to this present finding, research by Victor-Aigbodion Vera in Edo State, Nigeria, on the relationship between parenting styles and academic motivation among in-school adolescents stated that permissive parenting style has non-significant positive relation with academic motivation.

The findings also stated that negligent parenting style has a non-significant positive relationship with academic motivation and non-significant negative effect with amotivation in the sample setting. But a study in Edo state by Victor-Aigbodion Vera concluded that negligent parenting style has negative effects on student's academic motivation.

To conclude, there is a non-significant relationship between parenting styles and academic motivation. This may be because the questionnaire used for collecting parenting styles was in the Indian context but the academic motivation scale is for a western setting. Even though the AMS has been proved to have good psychometrics in the Indian context, there are some questions which is concerned about the student's likes of career choice but in India, LinkedIn research shows that 82% of Indian parents are involved in their children's career decisions which makes the child to lose their confidence in their decision-making skills.

From this study we can make sure one thing that there are very limited number of studies in the topic parenting styles in India. To make them more aware of the concept of parenting styles and its positive and negative outcomes, more research to be done in this field, especially in Asian countries. The concept, parenting style vary culture to culture so in future it is suggested that research could be done in and around Asian countries to find the relationship between parenting style and other factors that are affected by it.

Future directions:

- Future research should consider a larger sample size from multiple schools in different geographical locations in and around India, so that it would be more accurate and more evenly distribute results representing the parenting styles and academic motivation levels.
- Future researchers may collect data from more periods to examine the effect of parenting styles on students' academic motivation to find the results for long-term effects.
- Future research may include other possible variables that affect academic motivation.

Implications:

This study made awareness about how parents' parenting styles and students perceived parenting styles of their parents are important in their academic factors. So, the concerned bodies such as the PTA of educational institutions can provide awareness on promoting the positive and negative outcomes of different parenting styles.

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Conflict of Interests:

The author(s) declared no conflict of interests.

REFERENCES

- Baumrind D. Child care practices anteceding three patterns of preschool behavior. *Genetic Psychology Monographs*. 1967;75(1):43-88.
- Buoy, M. M. (2013). The influence of parental involvement on academic motivation and achievement in college students.
- Darling, N., & Steinberg, L. (1993). Parenting style as context: An integrative model. *Psychological bulletin*, 113(3), 487.
- Dordi, M. M., & Pol, M. S. (2018). Relationship of parenting styles with personality and academic motivation among adolescents. *International Journal of Indian Psychology*, 6(1), 152-159.
- Dr. Ranjeet Kumar, "BIHAR KE PRAMUKH KISAN ANDOLAN ", *International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT)*, ISSN:2320-2882, Volume.5, Issue 2, pp.168-171, June 2017
- Gafoor, Kunnathodi & Kurukkan, Abidha. (2014). Construction and Validation of Scale of Parenting Style. *Guru Journal of Behavioural Sciences*. 2. 315-323.
- Hoang, T. N. (2007). The Relations between Parenting and Adolescent Motivation. *International Journal of whole schooling*, 3(2), 1-21.
- Khan T, Ilyas M (2020) Role of authoritative and authoritarian parenting styles in academic motivation among students. *IOSR Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. 25:61–67
- Li, P. (2016, December 3). What Is Authoritative Parenting? (Examples and Comparisons). Retrieved March 10, 2023, from Parenting for Brain website: <https://www.parentingforbrain.com/authoritative-parenting/>
- Maccoby, E.E., & Martin, J.A. (1983). Socialization in the context of the family: Parent-child interaction. In P. Mussen and E.M. Hetherington, editors, *Handbook of Child Psychology*, volume IV: Socialization, personality, and social development. New York: Wiley.
- McClelland, D.C. (1953) *The Achievement Motive*. Appleton-Century-Crofts, New York.
- <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/11144-000>
- Mihret, A. M., Dilgasa, G. S., & Mamo, T. H. (2019). Parenting style as correlates of adolescents' academic achievement motivation of bate secondary school, Haramaya, Ethiopia. *International Journal of Education and Literacy Studies*, 7(2), 172-176.
- Rangarajan J, Narasimhan U, Janakiraman A, Sasidharan P, Chandrasekaran P. Parenting Styles of Parents Who Had Children With and Without High Risk at Birth: A Cross-sectional Comparative Study. *Cureus*. 2020 Feb 23;12(2): e7079. doi: 10.7759/cureus.7079. PMID: 32226680; PMCID: PMC7093920.
- Rivers, J., Mullis, A. K., Fortner, L. A., & Mullis, R. L. (2012). Relationships between parenting styles and the academic performance of adolescents. *Journal of Family Social Work*, 15(3), 202-216.

- Roy Chowdhury, Satyabrata & Mandal, Koyel & Das, Suchandra & Datta, Kalpana & Datta, Supratim. (2021). Study to determine the relationship between parenting style and adolescent self-esteem. *IP Journal of Paediatrics and Nursing Science*. 3. 112-117. 10.18231/j.ijpns.2020.021.
- Rubin, S. N. (2017). *The relationship between academic motivation and parenting styles in multiple socioeconomic status areas*. Rowan University.
- Ryan, R. M., & Deci, E. L. (2000). Self-determination theory and the facilitation of intrinsic motivation, social development, and well-being. *American Psychologist*, 55(1), 68–78. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0003-066X.55.1.68>
- Tang, J., Li, N., Sandoval, J. R., & Liu, Y. (2018). Parenting styles and academic motivation: A sample from Chinese high schools. *Journal of Child and Family Studies*, 27(10), 3395–3401.
- Turner, E. A., Chandler, M., & Heffer, R. W. (2009). The influence of parenting styles, achievement motivation, and self-efficacy on academic performance in college students. *Journal of college student development*, 50(3), 337-346.
- Vallerand, R.J., Blais, M.R., Brière, N.M., & Pelletier, L.G. (1989). Construction et validation de l'Échelle de Motivation en Éducation (EME). *Revue canadienne des sciences du comportement*, 21, 323-349.
- Victor-Aigboidion, V., Ugwoke, N. D., Ogechi, N., & Justina, A. (2020). PARENTING STYLES AS CORRELATES OF ACADEMIC MOTIVATION AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL ADOLESCENTS IN EDO STATE. *Journal of the Nigerian Council of Educational Psychologists*, 13(1).